

A SECURITY SYSTEM TO REMOVE MALICIOUS WEBPAGES ON MOBILE USING KAYO

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Abstract:

Mobile specific web pages differ significantly from their desktop counterparts in content, screen size, layout and functionality. In existing techniques to detect malicious websites are to work for such WebPages Only. In this paper, we design and implement kAYO, a mechanism that distinguishes between malicious mobile WebPages. Various methodologies are proposed to detect the malicious websites based on features like web contents, HTML codes, session information, and dynamic behaviours. We then apply kAYO to a dataset of over 350,000 known benign and malicious mobile web pages and demonstrate 90% accuracy in classification. Moreover, we discover, characterize and report a number of web pages missed by Google Safe Browsing and Virus Total, but detected by kAYO. Finally, we build a browser extension using kAYO to protect users from malicious mobile websites in real-time. In doing so, we provide the first static analysis technique to detect malicious.

Key Words: Malicious Websites, Web Browser, Machine Learning & Mobile Security

1. Introduction:

Mobile devices are increasingly being used to access the web. However, in spite of significant advances in processor power and bandwidth, the browsing experience on mobile devices is considerably different. These differences can largely be attributed to the dramatic reduction of screen size, which impacts the content, functionality and layout of mobile web pages. Identify the malicious URLs based on dynamically extracted lexical patterns from URLs. They developed a new method to mine their URL patterns, which are not assembled using any pre-defined items and thus cannot be mined using any existing frequent pattern mining methods. It can provide new flexibility and capability malicious URLs algorithmically generated by malicious programs. Content, functionality and layout have regularly been used to perform static analysis to determine maliciousness in the desktop space. Features such as the frequency of iframes and the number of redirections have traditionally served as strong indicators of malicious intent. Due to the significant changes made to accommodate mobile devices, such assertions may no longer be true. For example, whereas such behavior would be flagged as suspicious in the desktop setting, many popular benign mobile web pages require multiple redirections before users gain access to content. Previous techniques also fail to consider mobile specific webpage elements such as calls to mobile APIs. For instance, links that spawn the phone's dialer (and the reputation of the number itself) can provide strong evidence of the intent of the page. New tools are therefore necessary to identify malicious pages in the mobile web. In this paper, we present kAYO. The coming and the rising fame of systems, Internet, intranets and conveyed frameworks, security is getting to be one of the central purposes of exploration. Web substance is experiencing a critical change.

Figure: Types of Malicious URL Detection Methods

2. Related Work:

2.1 Exposure: Finding Malicious Domains Using Passive DNS Analysis: The domain name service (DNS) plays an important role in the operation of the Internet, providing a two-way mapping between domain names and their numerical identifiers. Given its fundamental role, it is not surprising that a wide variety of malicious activities involve the domain name service in one way or another. Thus, it seems beneficial to monitor the use of the DNS system for signs that indicate that a certain name is used as part of a malicious operation.

2.2 All Your Iframes Point to us: As the web continues to play an ever increasing role in information exchange, so too is it becoming the prevailing platform for infecting vulnerable hosts. A detailed study of the

pervasiveness of so-called drive-by downloads on the Internet. Drive by downloads are caused by URLs that attempt to exploit their visitors and cause malware to be installed and run automatically. Over a period of 10 months processed billions of URLs, and our results shows that a non-trivial amount, of over 3 million malicious URLs, initiate drive by downloads. An even more troubling finding is that approximately 1.3% of the incoming search queries to Google's search engine returned at least one URL labeled as malicious in the results page. Specifically, we study the relationship between the user browsing habits and exposure to malware, the techniques used to lure the user into the malware distribution networks, and the different properties of these networks. Drawback is downloading and executing each webpage impacts performance and hinders scalability of dynamic approaches.

2.3 A Framework for Detection and Measurement of Phishing Attacks: Phishing is form of identity theft that combines social engineering techniques and sophisticated attack vectors to harvest financial information from unsuspecting consumers. Often a phisher tries to lure her victim into clicking a URL pointing to a rogue page. The structure of URLs employed in various phishing attacks. We find that it is often possible to tell whether or not a URL belongs to a phishing attack without requiring any knowledge of the corresponding page data. several features that can be used to distinguish a phishing URL from a benign one. These features are used to model a logistic regression filter that is efficient and has a high accuracy. We use this filter to perform thorough measurements on several million URLs and quantify the prevalence of phishing on the Internet today. Drawback is URL-based techniques usually suffer from high false positive rates.

2.4 A Content-Based Approach to Detecting Phishing Web Sites: Phishing is a significant problem involving fraudulent email and web sites that trick unsuspecting users into revealing private information, the design, implementation, and evaluation of CANTINA, a novel, content-based approach to detecting phishing web sites, based on the TF-IDF information retrieval algorithm. The design and evaluation of several heuristics we developed to reduce false positives. CANTINA is good at detecting phishing sites, correctly labeling approximately 95% of phishing sites. CANTINA has comparable or better performance to Spoof Guard (a heuristic-based anti-phishing tool) with far fewer false positives, and does about as well as Net Craft (a blacklist and heuristic-based anti-phishing toolbar). Finally, we show that CANTINA combined with heuristics is effective at detecting phishing URLs in users' actual email, and that its most frequent mistake is labeling spam-related URLs as phishing. Drawback is Cantina suffers from performance problems due to the time lag involved in querying the Google search engine.

2.5 Prophiler: a Fast Filter for the Large-Scale Detection of Malicious Web Pages: Malicious web pages that host drive-by-download exploits have become a popular means for compromising hosts on the Internet and, subsequently, for creating large-scale botnets. In a drive-by download exploit, an attacker embeds a malicious script (typically written in JavaScript) into a web page. When a victim visits this page, the script is executed and attempts to compromise the browser or one of its plug-in. To detect drive-by-download exploits, researchers have developed a number of systems that analyze web pages for the presence of malicious code. In this paper, we describe the design and implementation of such a filter. Our filter, called Prophiler, uses static analysis techniques to quickly examine a web page for malicious content. This analysis takes into account features derived from the HTML contents of a page, from the associated JavaScript code, and from the corresponding URL. We automatically derive detection models that use these features using machine-learning techniques applied to labeled datasets. Drawback is Malicious desktop websites will work well on mobile websites is yet to be explored. Cantina does not work well on WebPages written in languages other than English. Finally, existing techniques do not account for new mobile threats such as known fraud phone numbers that attempt to trigger the dialer on the phone.

3. Methodology:

Our objective is to design and develop a technique to identify mobile specific malicious web pages in real-time. We extract static features from webpage. We predictions about its potential maliciousness. We first discuss the feature set used in kAYO followed by the collection process of the dataset.

3.1 kAYO Feature Set: A webpage has several components including HTML and JavaScript code, images, the URL, and the header. Mobile specific web pages also access applications running on a user's device using web APIs (e.g., the dialer). We extract structural, lexical and quantitative properties of such components to generate kAYO's feature set. We focus on extracting mobile relevant features that take minimal extraction time. Our hypothesis is that such features are strong indicators of whether a webpage has been built for assisting a user in their web browsing experience or for malicious purposes. We divide kAYO's 44 features into four classes: mobile specific-, JavaScript, HTML and URL features. To the best of our knowledge, we are the first to use these mobile specific features, and do not claim novelty on using subsets of other previously identified features.

3.2 Mobile Specific Features: We collect eight mobile specific feature to capture the advanced capabilities of mobile web pages. Mobile websites enable access to personal data from a user's phone, an experience not offered by desktop websites In order to characterize the behaviour of mobile API calls ,we extracted the number of API calls tel:, smsto:, mms: and mmsto: from each mobile webpage. We further extracted the target phone numbers from these API calls. We ran the commercially available pindrop security phone reputation system

(PRS) on each phone number. Based on the results of PRS, we gave the score of 1/0 (known fraud/benign) to each phone number scraped from the mobile API calls, and added the score as a feature in KAYO. We only extracted phone numbers with API prefixes that could trigger an application installed on a user's phone. We did not consider phone number strings simply listed on web pages without an API prefix.

Figure 2: System architecture of kayo

3.3 JavaScript Features: JavaScript enable client-side user interaction, asynchronous communication with servers, and modification of the DOM objects of webpage on the fly. We extract 10 features that capture the JavaScript relevant static behaviour of a web page, two of which are new. All the features are faster to extract than the features based on JavaScript de-obfuscation. JavaScript found on malicious web pages can be obfuscated. Instead of de-obfuscating every JavaScript, we extract simple JavaScript related features from a webpage. The primary reason in choosing this approach is that a large number of benign web pages include potentially dangerous JavaScript code as shown by Yee. For example, 44% of the top 6,805 websites from Alexa use the potentially dangerous JavaScript function. These observations invalidate the assumption made in existing techniques; that potentially dangerous JavaScript keywords are more frequently used in malicious web pages.

3.4 HTML Features: We extract 14 features in total from the HTML code of each webpage. Popular web pages include a number of images, and internal and external HTML links for better user experience. For example, the top-level page of m.cnn.com includes links to other news articles published by CNN (international HTML links), advertisements for a local restaurant (external HTML link) and images related to the latest breaking news. Accordingly, we first determine whether a webpage has any images, internal and external HTML links. We then extract the number of internal links, external links and images from a webpage as features of KAYO. The distribution of iframes on mobile web pages is different as compared to that on desktop web pages. However, we do not rule out the possibility of a mobile malicious webpage including malicious content in iframe and consider the presence and number of iframe in a webpage as features in KAYO. Past research also shows that malicious websites take several redirections before leading the user to the target webpage to avoid DNS based detection.

3.5 URL Features: Structural and lexical properties of a URL have been used to differentiate between malicious and benign web pages. However, using only URL features for such differentiation leads to a high false positive rate. We extract 12 URL features in total. Authors of phishing web pages often exploit the familiarity of users to a webpage by including words in the URL that can mislead a user into believing that the phishing webpage is the legitimate webpage. Words such as login and bank are commonly used in the URL of the login webpage for benign websites that are highly prone to phishing. Only a part of the small screen. Therefore, intuitively, the author of a phishing webpage will include misleading words at the beginning of the URL. We consider the presence of such words in the URL as a new feature in KAYO.

4. Implementation and Evaluation:

We describe the machine learning techniques we considered to tackle the problem of classifying mobile specific web pages as malicious or benign. We then discuss the strengths and weaknesses of each classification technique, and the process for selecting the best model for kAYO. We build and evaluate our chosen model for accuracy, false positive rate and true positive rate. Finally, we compare kAYO to existing techniques and empirically demonstrate the significance of kAYO's features. We note that where automated analysis is possible.

5. Scope of the Problem:

The approaches to detect the malicious websites fall into three categories. Static, dynamic and hybrid (combination of static and dynamic analysis). The static approaches rely on the features of URL (path, domain, sub-domain), host information, malicious web contents and presence of particular tokens in the URL. The

dynamic approach captures the behaviours for classification. Some approach dynamically extracts the lexical pattern for analysis. The third approach hybrid uses both static and dynamic methods. The static methods are used for initial classification and dynamic approaches are used to ensure the correctness of the classification. The performance of the detection is improved in this method. The commonly used protection technique is blacklisting of known malicious URLs and IP address collected through manual reporting, data sources, honey part and custom analysis techniques. This approach uses various lexical features of URL.

6. Conclusion and Future Enhancement:

Mobile web pages are significantly different than their desktop counterparts in content, functionality and lay- out. Therefore, existing techniques using static features of desktop web pages to detect malicious behavior do not work well for mobile specific pages. We designed and developed a fast and reliable static analysis technique called kAYO that detects mobile malicious web pages. KAYO provides 90% accuracy in classification, and detects a number of malicious mobile web pages in the wild that are not detected by existing techniques such as Google Safe Browsing and Virus Total. Finally, we build a browser extension using kAYO that We conclude kAYO detects new mobile specific threats such as websites hosting known fraud numbers and takes the first step towards identifying new security challenges in the modern mobile web. In future we implement more web pages on mobile.

7. References:

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